

DETERMINATION OF LEFT VENTRICULAR DIASTOLIC FUNCTION AND CORRECTION OF CHANGES IN PATIENTS WITH CORONARY HEART DISEASE

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Summary. AH and IHD are the main causes of LVDD and diastolic HF (MareevV.Yu., 2003). Violation of LV LV in patients with AH has a multifactorial nature and does not occur in isolation, but simultaneously with a violation of the morphofunctional state of other organs and systems, or with their pathogenetic participation, due to prolonged exposure to high blood pressure.

Key words: arterial hypertension. arterial pressure, ischemic heart disease, left ventricular ejection fraction.

Actuality: Every year, more than 17 million people die from cardiovascular diseases worldwide, and more than half of them are patients with coronary heart disease (CHD). Despite advances in instrumental diagnosis and treatment, coronary heart disease remains the most common disease among people of working age, causing high disability and mortality. [4]. Currently, it has been proven that diastolic disorders are the cause of HF in about 30-40% of cases [3]. Moreover, there is evidence that violations of the diastolic properties of the myocardium usually precede a decrease in LV pumping function and can even lead to the appearance of symptoms of HF in isolation [2].

Violation of DFLJ in patients with hypertension has a multifactorial nature and does not occur in isolation, but simultaneously with a violation of the morphofunctional state of other organs and systems, or with their pathogenetic participation, due to prolonged exposure to high blood pressure. This dictates the need to find new combinations of medications and put them into practice to prevent the progression of coronary heart disease and improve the quality of life of these patients.

The purpose of the study. Based on the above, the aim of the study was to find new pathogenesis mechanisms, develop criteria for clinical and functional classification and give a comparative assessment of various types of treatment of left ventricular diastolic dysfunction in patients with coronary artery disease.

Materials and methods of research. The study included patients aged no older than 70 years with a stable course of coronary heart disease (CHD) during

the previous month, with a left ventricular ejection fraction (LVEF) of at least 45%. A mandatory criterion was the presence of a stable sinus rhythm in the patient.

The results of the study and their discussion. The features of the AH syndrome that contribute to the development of LDL are the duration of its existence in the presence of a high level and daily load, both SAD and DAD, increased variability of blood pressure during the day, the absence of a decrease, an increase and a high load of blood pressure at night, as well as a high rate of morning rise in blood pressure.

In the presence of LVL in patients with hypertension, microalbuminuria occurs 6 times more often than with normal LV relaxation, while the identification of correlations between the fact of detection of microalbuminuria and the indicators of LVL does not mean the direct participation of microalbuminuria in the pathogenesis of impaired relaxation, but indicates the synchronous development of two processes - morphofunctional LV restructuring and nephropathy, equally dependent from the severity of the AH syndrome, in particular from the absence of a nocturnal decrease in blood pressure.

In the majority of patients with hypertension, DD developed against the background of LV remodeling by the type of concentric hypertrophy with a tendency, in the presence of volume overload, to form eccentric hypertrophy, and high correlations reliably confirmed the dependence of the development of LVL on an increase in LV myocardial mass.

The development of endothelial dysfunction in hypertension is facilitated by a decrease in endothelium-dependent vasodilation and a 1.36-fold increase in the serum concentration of endothelin-1, as well as vascular remodeling with an increase in the thickness of the intima-media complex and the stiffness of the artery walls.

Long-term hypertension with a predominant increase in the level, variability and daily load of SAD contributes to the development of DC AK, which is accompanied by an increase in the systolic velocity of aortic blood flow and the pressure gradient between the LV and the aorta and is an independent risk factor for both hypertrophic remodeling and LV DD, progressing as the number of calcified valves increases, which does not allow even moderate DC can be considered a benign process.

Conclusion. New criteria have been developed for determining the stage of LVD based on Doppler echocardiographic examination of high-amplitude

reflected motion signals and parameters of transmitral blood flow, as well as assessment of clinical and functional factors: features of the daily blood pressure profile, the severity of MAU, the nature and degree of LV and peripheral vascular remodeling, the degree of endothelial dysfunction, HRV changes, as well as the presence and prevalence of concomitant DCAC.

The effectiveness of the use of myocardial cytoprotector trimetazidine for normalization of global and regional LVD caused by ischemia and myocardial hibernation has been proven.

The combined therapy with IAPFENALAPRIL and Aatlozartan has been proven to be more effective in the reverse development of LV remodeling and normalization of DFLJ, compared with monotherapy with each of these drugs separately.

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